

Studies on the Sorption and Desorption of Methylene Blue on Kaolinite

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The adsorption data of methylene blue (MB) on kaolinite fit in with the Langmuir equation up to 10^{-4} M dye concentration studied. The selectivity and distribution coefficients calculated from desorption of MB by inorganic and organic cations are in the order: $\text{Na}^+ < \text{NH}_4^+ < \text{K}^+ < \text{H}^+ < \text{Ca}^{2+} < \text{Ba}^{2+} < \text{cetyltrimethylammonium ion} < \text{cetyl pyridinium ion}$.

Systematic studies of cation exchange in pure clay minerals carried out by different investigators reveal that certain specificities in the exchange behaviour may be traced to their characteristic lattice configuration^{1,2,3}. Specificities such as the "cation effects" have been pointed out by Mitra⁴ and Mukherjee⁵. Most of the earlier investigations on exchange equilibria, selectivity etc. were primarily based on the results of interactions of clays with inorganic cations⁶. Our knowledge about the clay-organic ion interaction is still meagre, the physico-chemical aspects of many of these reactions being still unknown in all their fundamental details. Thus, it has been noted⁷ that the interaction between organic bases and clay minerals is not reversible in the same sense as it is applied to most of the inorganic cations. It is in this context that an attempt has been made in the present investigation to study the sorption and desorption characteristics of methylene blue (MB) on kaolinite.

EXPERIMENTAL

A kaolinite fraction having particle size minus 2.0μ was isolated and collected from Rajmahal kaolinite (supplied by Calcutta Minerals Supply Co. Ltd.) by the usual method of dispersion and sedimentation. It was converted into the H-form by H-resin (Amberlite IR-120) treatment. The adsorption of MB by H-kaolinite was studied first. A known amount of kaolinite suspension was taken in a number of test tubes and different amounts of MB (E. Merck) solution were added. The test tubes were then shaken and kept overnight. The pH of the suspensions before and after adsorption of the dye varied between 4.1 and 4.5. The supernatant liquid was decanted off and centrifuged at 2000 rpm for 30

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minutes or so. The MB content was analysed from absorbance measurements with supernatant liquids using the Spekkar absorptiometer (Hilger).

The kaolinite was next mixed with MB having a concentration equivalent roughly to two times the *bec.* (base exchange capacity) of the mineral. After 24 hours of equilibration the excess MB was washed with distilled water till the washed liquid showed a constant optical density. The MB-complex was then brought to suspension in water and the colloid content subsequently determined by drying a definite volume at 110° for 24 hours. 10 ml portions of the suspension (1.63%) of MB-kaolinite complex were taken in a number of test tubes and varying amounts of different electrolytes were added. The total volume was kept the same in all the tubes by adding water. The equilibrium concentration of the desorbing ions was not allowed to exceed 0.02 M. The mixtures were then shaken and allowed to equilibrate overnight. The supernatant liquid was decanted off and centrifuged for half an hour. The MB content was determined as above.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A typical adsorption isotherm of MB on kaolinite is shown in Fig. 1. The adsorption data are seen to fit in well with the Langmuir equation suggesting monolayer adsorption. The exchange capacity equal to 5.2 m.e./100 gm determined by titration of H-kaolinite with barium hydroxide in presence of N-barium chloride agrees well with 5.6 m.e.

FIG. 1. (a) Adsorption isotherm of methylene blue on Kaolinite.

(b) Fitting of the data in the Langmuir adsorption equation.

estimated from MB adsorption data. Ramchandran, Kacker and Patwardhan⁸ also observed an agreement between the MB method and ammonium-acetate method for measurement of *bec.* From adsorption data the area per exchange site of kaolinite calculated by them was $38.7\text{\AA}^2$ which is almost equal to the area associated the MB molecule, namely, $39.2\text{\AA}^2$. This means that there is no overlapping of the adsorbed MB molecules. The slightly higher value of the *bec.* estimated from MB adsorption data may be due to adsorption of MB on glass surface⁹. It may be mentioned here that dye-dye interaction¹⁰ at low concentration of MB studied may be neglected.

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STUDIES ON THE SORPTION AND DESORPTION OF METHYLENE BLUE ON KAOLINITE 745

The results of calculation of selectivity and distribution coefficients are given in table I, and the relevant desorption data are presented in Figs. 2 and 3. In the equilibrium $M\bar{B} + \frac{1}{z} i z^+ \rightleftharpoons \frac{1}{z} i z^+ + MB$ where the bar denotes the species in the solid phase, and Z the valency of the ion i, the distribution coefficient is given by $\lambda_i = \frac{m_i}{m_1}$, where m_i , m_1 are the molal concentrations of the species in the solid and liquid phases, and the selectivity coefficient is given by $K_{iMB} = \frac{[MB] [i^{z+}]^1/z}{[M\bar{B}] [i^{z+}]^1/z}$. The values of the distribution coefficients and the selectivity coefficients are calculated in Table I for the ions Na^+ , K^+ , NH_4^+ , H^+ , Ca^{2+} , Ba^{2+} and trisethylenediamine cobalt³⁺ ($Co en_3^{3+}$)³⁺ and also for cetyltrimethylammonium (CTA^+) and cetyl pyridinium ion (CP^+). The selectivity coefficients are in the order: $Na^+ < NH_4^+ < K^+ < H^+ < Ca^{2+} < Ba^{2+} < Co en_3^{3+} \ll CTA^+ < CP^+$.

FIG. 2. Desorption data of MB from kaolinite MB complex by different ions 1-Ba²⁺, 2-Ca²⁺, 3-H⁺, 4-K⁺, 5-NH₄⁺, 6-Na⁺.

FIG. 3. Desorption data of MB from kaolinite-MB complex by quaternary ammonium ions. 1-CP⁺, 2-CTA⁺, 3-(Coen₃)³⁺

TABLE I

Electrolyte used	Conc. of electrolyte	Distribution co-efficient	Selectivity co-efficient.
1:1 electrolytes			
NaCl	1.4 × 10 ⁻³	2.9 × 10 ⁻³	1.7 × 10 ⁻⁸
NH ₄ Cl	"	3.7 × 10 ⁻³	4.5 × 10 ⁻⁸
KCl	"	5.2 × 10 ⁻³	9.0 × 10 ⁻⁸
HCl	"	5.9 × 10 ⁻³	1.2 × 10 ⁻⁷
2:1 electrolytes			
CaCl ₂	"	7.2 × 10 ⁻³	2.07 × 10 ⁻⁶
BaCl ₂	"	8.6 × 10 ⁻³	2.76 × 10 ⁻⁶
3:1 electrolyte			
(Coen ₃)Cl ₃	3.9 × 10 ⁻³	6.6 × 10 ⁻³	2.62 × 10 ⁻³
Quaternary ammonium salts			
CTAB	1.1 × 10 ⁻³	8.3	2.2 × 10 ⁻⁴
OPCl	"	13.5	6.7 × 10 ⁻⁴

It is observed that the large quaternary cations desorb MB from its kaolinite-complex several thousand times more strongly than the inorganic cations. This may be ascribed to

strong adsorbability¹¹, geometrical relationship to surfaces, surface-active property,¹² and stronger affinity of the quaternary ions for the altered clay surface. Comparing their selectivity and distribution coefficients corresponding to 1.1×10^{-3} M which is almost equal to the cmc of CTAB it is observed that CPCI having a lower cmc (0.8×10^{-3}) is a more efficient desorbing agent.

The error of measurement lies within $\pm 10\%$ caused primarily by inaccuracy involved in the analysis of MB. Error due to adsorption on the walls has been reduced by using vessels of pyrex glass which is known to adsorb little of MB. A possible interaction of the dye with the surface active ions¹³ may be negligible in the range of the electrolyte concentration studied.

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